

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Том 2, Выпуск 2, 29 Февраль

TECHNOLOGY OF MORAL AND MORAL EDUCATION OF THE FUTURE TEACHER OF PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT: The moral and moral education of the future teacher of vocational education was based on the scientific and theoretical aspects of the actual pedagogical problem; the personality of the teacher of vocational education and their role in spiritual and moral education were analyzed pedagogically, its content and essence were covered; the content, forms and methods of spiritual and moral education of the future teacher of; pedagogical conditions, conclusions and recommendations of moral and moral education of the future teacher of professional education were developed.

The universal and methodological recommendations developed in the course of the study can be widely used in all parts of the system of continuous education, in the process of teaching and improving social sciences, in the implementation of spiritual and educational work in educational institutions.

The materials of the research work can be widely used by such scientists as pedagogues, historians, philosophers, psychologists dealing with the problems of education, morality, spirituality, in the training of higher educational institutions, professional colleges, in the courses of professional development and retraining of teachers, as well as employees of public education, teachers.

Keywords: thought, professional education, spiritual, moral education, humanitarian, universal, development, education, moral, teacher, vocational education, scientific aspects, theoretical aspects, actual, pedagogical problem, the personality, analyze, the content, pedagogical conditions, conclusion, recommendation, comparative-critical study, analysis of scientific and methodological literature on political, philosophical, historical, ethnographic, pedagogical, psychological and spiritual; pedagogical observation, interview, questionnaire survey; tests, experiment-test; monitoring, mathematical-statistical analysis; summarizing the results of the research, "public education", "continuous education", "pedagogical skills", "vocational education", temperament, intelligence, "spiritual-moral upbringing", common sense, kindness, purity, honesty, conscientiousness, love for Labor, loyalty to the motherland, conscience, duty, faith, kindness, compassion, mutual assistance, humanism, kindness, faith, " pedagogy";

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pedagogical skills", " professional pedagogy", " pedagogical technologies ", IT knowledge, confidence, worldview, national ideology, the idea of national independence, Independence, Organization, initiative, creativity, questionability, resourcefulness, nobility, loyalty to their profession, Comparative analysis, self-assessment, rating, tests, observation, conversation, questionnaire, creation of problematic situations, as noted above, future, willpower, enthusiasm, courage, self-confidence.

INTRODUCTION: The main idea of the people of our country on the path of national development is the restoration of a free and prosperous, free and prosperous life. Of course, the development of political, economic, social and spiritual directions plays an important role in the implementation of this idea. And it's no secret to anyone that the development of these lines still depends on the personnel that are being prepared for today. In Fact, The President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan I.A.The great attention given to the education system and the conditions created at the initiative of Karimov personally in the following years are the main grounds for the comprehensive development of the future generation. Our compatriot is our main task "...it consists in educating a perfect person – a harmonious person who has an independent worldview, who lives on the basis of the invaluable heritage of our ancestors and modern thinking."

In the spiritual and moral education of the younger generation, effective organizational, pedagogical forms and tools based on rich cultural and historical traditions, customs and universal values of the people are developed and introduced into practice in the "national program of Personnel Training" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The priority of educating the individual and bringing him to perfection in every possible way is ensured. In order to increase the general and pedagogical culture, spiritual and educational work between the country's morality will be improved." Also in this program, it is indicated the need to pay attention to "ensuring the humanitarian direction of education on the basis of the rich spiritual and spiritual heritage of the people and universal values" in the training of morally and morally competent specialists.

The idea of national independence and democracy, national and scientific worldview on the basis of national and universal values, high spirituality and democratic culture, economic, legal and creative thinking, Judaism and socio-political activity on the basis of Humanities and socio-economic sciences taught in higher educational institutions, especially in the content of the disciplines in the pedagogical cycle, in a word, the need Such directions as the development of spiritual values in the minds of young people, the restoration of the invaluable spiritual and cultural heritage created by our

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ancestors, the positive essence of spiritual recovery, the creation of the necessary conditions for the formation of a spiritually rich personality, the formation of high spirituality, culture and creative thinking, pride and a sense of human dignity, the Of course, without the formation of the main directions of spiritual and moral education, such as the prosperity of the Motherland, the peace of the people, a perfect person, social cooperation, the harmony of the nation, tolerance of religion, one can not educate a true professional person. Society dictates the upbringing and development of people loyal to their profession, skilled. Because the restoration of a free and prosperous, free and prosperous life is the main idea of the people of Uzbekistan on the path of national development, it is the most basic task of every student to deeply avoid and actively participate in its strengthening. Therefore, it is one of the important issues to educate the students in every possible way, to give them spiritual and educational knowledge, to create skills and qualifications. Although certain work experiences have been accumulated in this area and some shortcomings have also been identified in the work in this direction, the pedagogical solution to the problem has not sufficiently expressed itself in the theory of Education.

A single, consistent system of organizing the process of spiritual and moral education of higher education students has not been developed. Special literature on the formation of this sphere is not enough.

The results of the study of the work of higher educational institutions that train pedagogical personnel showed that there are some problems in the organization and management of the process of moral and moral education of students. Therefore, in our study, we drew attention to the coverage of the problem of moral and moral education of future teachers of vocational education, the creation of its scientific and pedagogical bases.

MATERIALS

Spiritual and moral education of young people has become the main task of society in every era. Because the spirituality of a people whose moral purity, personality is beautiful, is also considered high. It is also worth noting that the Uzbek people have long been world-famous for their spirituality and culture. Middle Asian thinkers such as Abu Nasr Forabi, Abu Rayhon Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Alisher Navoi made a huge contribution to the development of the culture of our people and enrichment of spirituality. In their works, they clearly expressed the goals and tasks of bringing a person to the level of originality, virtue, perfection. The invaluable works of our great ancestors

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are the basis of our spirituality and the negation of the spiritual and moral upbringing of the reader-youth.

The issues of formation of the spirituality of the reader-youth, upbringing them in the spirit of national and universal values, as well as improvement of moral aspects o.Musurmonova, Sh.Qurbanov, U.Court, J.G'.Yoldoshev, N.Artiqov, M.Report This WebsiteHasanbaev, M.Ochilov, K.Z.Zaripov, Sh.Shodmonova, D.Rozieva, Sh.Sh.Olimov made his own expression in the scientific research of such scientists.

Improving the training of teachers of Labor and vocational education-problems of motivation R.H.Djuraev, P.T.Magzumov, U.N.Noshaliev, N.Saidaxmedov, O'.Q.Tolipov, A.R.Khodjabayev, E.T.Choriev, U.I.Inayatov, N.A.Muslimov, Z.K.Ismailova, A.A.Abduqodirov, X.F.It was studied by the rashidovs. The result of carrying out scientific research and observing the work experiences in this regard has shown that the problem of moral and moral education of future professional teachers has not been specially studied scientifically. The legislation on the creation of pedagogical conditions for moral and moral education of the future teacher of Professional Education has not been sufficiently studied in the theory of pedagogical science. Today, thanks to the independence of Uzbekistan, in the process of national education, there are all opportunities for solving the problems of moral and moral education of future teachers of vocational education.

Indeed, in the conditions of independence, on the basis of a new methodological basis, it is important to influence the individual both internally and externally, spiritual and moral education of future teachers of professional education on the basis of its social essence, structure of activity, self-awareness. Therefore, we defined the subject of the dissertation as "the technology of moral and moral education of the future teacher of professional education" (on the example of teaching subjects in the pedagogical direction).

METHODS

The research work was carried out on the basis of the scientific research work carried out at the Bukhara Institute of high technologies engineering and technical on the priority direction of the development of Science and technology in the direction of "spiritual-moral and cultural development of democratic and Legal Society, formation of innovative economy" of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic

Purpose of the study: to create methodological recommendations on the development and implementation of theoretical and methodological framework of moral and moral education of future professional education teacher.

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Research objectives:

1. Scientific-theoretical justification of moral and moral education of the teacher of professional education as a pedagogical problem.
2. Development of the technology of moral and moral education of the future teacher of professional education.
3. To develop a model of moral and moral education of the teacher of future professional education.
4. To determine the effectiveness of the results of the study in the process of pedagogical experience-testing.
5. To develop methodical recommendations on moral and moral education of future professional education teacher.

Object of the study: the process of moral and moral education of a future professional education teacher.

Subject of the study: the content, effective forms and methods, tools of the process of moral and moral education of the future professional education teacher.

Research methods: comparative-critical study, analysis of scientific and methodological literature on political, philosophical, historical, ethnographic, pedagogical, psychological and spiritual; pedagogical observation, interview, questionnaire survey; tests, experiment-test; monitoring, mathematical-statistical analysis; summarizing the results of the research.

Methodological basis of the study: law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on Education", "National Program of Personnel Training", president of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. The methodological basis of the dissertation is independence and spirituality in the works of Karimov, theoretical views on education and education, teachings of Eastern thinkers and scientists of our Republic on spirituality, enlightenment, morality and perfect man.

Scientific hypothesis of the study: the process of moral and moral education of future professional education teacher will be effective, if any:

- if the process of spiritual and moral education of the future teacher of professional education is analyzed scientifically pedagogically and its factors are clearly defined;
- if the technology of moral and moral education of the future professional education teacher is developed and its possibilities are fully opened;
- if the advanced ideas of Central Asian thinkers, folk pedagogy, national traditions and traditions are widely used in spiritual and moral education;
- if the effective forms, methods, means of spiritual and moral education of the

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future teacher of vocational education are established and its holistic system is created;
- a high result can be achieved if scientific-methodological and practical recommendations of moral and moral education of teachers of professional education are developed.

The main cases that are brought to protection:

1. Scientific-pedagogical analysis of the fact that moral and moral education of the future teacher of professional education is a pedagogical problem.
2. The technology, forms and techniques of moral and moral education of the future teacher of professional education.
3. The model of moral and moral education of the teacher of the future professional education.
4. Criteria for determining the level of moral and moral upbringing of a future professional education teacher.
5. Scientific-methodological recommendations and practical conclusions on moral and moral education of the future teacher of professional education.

Theoretical and practical aspects of the study were popularized at scientific-practical conferences held at the Bukhara Institute of engineering and technology, Bukhara State University, Samarkand State University and other higher educational institutions of the Republic. The main content of the study was brought to the attention of the pedagogical public with the help of scientific articles published in the journals "public education", "continuous education", "pedagogical skills", "vocational education". Also, the results of the study were covered in a monograph called "technology of moral and moral education of the teacher of vocational education".

RESULTS

Spirituality-begins with enlightenment. And the basis of education is education. The formation of an educational-illiterate spiritual worldview is complex.

The political-social, economic-cultural development of society primarily depends on the person, on his spiritual-educational formation. In this regard, it is worth recognizing that the economic, cultural, political development of any society forms the basis of human intelligence, thinking, consciousness, will, social activity, its spirituality, views, moral and aesthetic knowledge, internal spiritual experiences and the meaning of life. A person who has no spiritual wealth can not be a harmonious person, and can not actively participate in the process of socio-economic development, as a society that has not previously determined its goals, tasks, future dreams, clearly understood its practical ways, methods, means has never been able to rise to the heights.

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To the concept of spirituality, I.A.Karimov gives such a definition in his book "High spirituality is an invincible force", in depth and in detail, summarizing previous experiences: "spirituality is an incomparable force that encourages a person to spiritual purification, to heartily grow up, makes the inner world of a person energetic, makes the whole of his will, awakens his conscience, is the criterion of all his views". The essence of spirituality comes from such moral and moral qualities as intelligence, contemplation of cognition, virtues of humanity-persistence, courage, care, cares, taste, ingenuity, and the possession of such characteristics is indicated in the expression of the desire, purpose of the people and nation of each period. And for any person - nation with such moral and moral qualities, he sought to improve the life of the workers and the morals he cared about, and tried to put the interests of the people, the nation, the state above his own benefit.

Due to the requirements of national independence, definitions that reveal the essence and meaning of spirituality, the social pedagogical essence of the concept of "upbringing a spiritually and morally harmonious person", have created many more. Based on this, we can not be mistaken if we describe as " spirituality is a force that reflects the intelligence, spiritual perfection, moral potential of a person, manifests itself in his worldview, prepares him as an active participant in socio - economic life, generalizes the ability, talent, experience of people."

Morality is inextricably linked with the concept of spirituality, it is one of the forms of social consciousness. Morality forms in young people such qualities as honesty, purity, duty, conscience, generosity, self-sacrifice. Morality is a complex of norms (norms) of conduct that regulate people's relations with themselves, their family, relatives, friends.

Morality is a unique way of knowing the world, regulating people's behavior from the point of view of good and evil. Morality has the function of forming norms of behavior, which are considered extremely important for a person, correctly approaching the world of social life, human cultural life, social values.

From the above points we can conclude that the concepts of "spirituality "and" morality " are close to each other and complement each other. These concepts are intertwined and represent all the positive qualities of a person, his morality, temperament, intelligence, inextricably linked ideological views. Therefore, we call it "spiritual-moral upbringing", combining both these words. Spiritual and moral qualities of a person are integrated into a person with the help of upbringing.

Spiritual and moral education in its own time embodied spiritual and moral concepts, the consciousness of a person is connected with society, nature, the duty of

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people before society, behavior-it is a social phenomenon that determines its relevance, its impact on society. In the content of spiritual and moral education lies such positive human qualities as intelligence, common sense, kindness, purity, honesty, conscientiousness, love for Labor, loyalty to the motherland.

Spiritual and moral education performs the following functions::

- formation of positive attitude of people towards society;
- educating conscious discipline;
- education of a perfect person;
- to evoke a sense of hatred for negative vices in society.

We tried to establish its definition, proceeding from the theoretical foundations of the essence of the moral and moral education of the teacher of the future professional education. That is, the moral and moral education of the teacher of the future professional education – this is the formation of strong spiritual and moral knowledge, skills and skills, the formation of a culture of human behavior, the formation of positive emotions, being an example in the implementation of norms of behavior, the attitude of a person to events taking place in society, observance of daily spiritual and moral principles and norms, the love of Vatan, the sense of Vatan, to bring happiness to members of the society by contributing, justice is a concept that embodies such positive qualities as conscience, duty, faith, kindness, compassion, mutual assistance, humanism, kindness, faith.

In the second chapter of the dissertation entitled "The methodology of spiritual and moral education of the future teacher of vocational education", the idea of the content of spiritual and moral education of the future teacher of vocational education on the basis of integration of pedagogical disciplines is discussed.

Moral and moral education of students is formed in the entire educational system of higher educational institutions. A special role in this process is played by subjects of pedagogical orientation. Teaching such subjects as " pedagogy", " pedagogical skills", " professional pedagogy", " pedagogical technologies " creates great opportunities for moral and moral education of teachers of future professional education. On the basis of the knowledge provided in these disciplines, there are opportunities to educate a specialist who has comprehensively developed, perfected, has an active life position, is able to organize mass-political work, is morally pure, jismonan harmonious, mentally thoughtful, has a deep theoretical-practical knowledge and spiritual-moral perfection in his specialty.

In the spiritual and moral education of teachers of the future professional education, the choice of educational materials for the lesson, the clear definition of the educational goals, taking into account the Real educational opportunities of teachers and students, the

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choice of interactive methods and tools that accurately and quickly convey the educational information to the student's mind, create a great Based on this, we have developed a system of lessons on the basis of interdisciplinary links aimed at "spiritual and moral education" of students with the help of topics included in the program of pedagogical category Sciences and additional information that allows them to convey the content to the minds of students. Bunda we have focused on the following features of the theme and information:

- to the modernity, relevance, science of subject and information;
- to be able to meet students ' level of preparation, requirements and needs;
- to the level of orientation of teacher and student attitude towards specific goals;
- we are guided by the rules on how to help students grow their educational and educational opportunities.

According to the law "on education", "national program of training of Personnel", one of the main directions of spiritual and educational work is in the reform of continuous education, in the development of the system of training of personnel. Because, in the upbringing of the younger generation, the effectiveness of educational work can not be achieved if moral and moral education is not met.

Spiritual and educational work, organized in higher educational institutions, contributes to the formation of the following qualities in the teachers of future professional education:

- spiritual and educational work is a continuation of educational work, which increases the moral and moral level of students;
- strengthens students ' spiritual and moral understanding, adds a new one;
- increases students ' respect for moral and moral values and develops their interesttiradi;
- increases the educational and educational activities of students.

Spiritual and educational activities allow students to understand life, to know it more deeply, to form in IT knowledge, confidence, worldview, national ideology, the idea of national independence, to grow in them such qualities as Independence, Organization, initiative, creativity, questionability, resourcefulness, nobility, loyalty to their profession.

DISCUSSION

The teacher of vocational education is the organizer and manager of the educational process in the vocational college. Its educational effect on students is realized in the process of being in circulation with the students in the course of training and extra-curricular times.

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It is a necessary phenomenon to develop a schematic structure of spiritual and moral education of a future professional education teacher. Because the structure is described as a system consisting of interrelated and mutually complementary components that ensure the interdependence of all forms of educational processes, represent the direction of the set goals and objectives and ensure the achievement of the intended results, each of the components listed in the structure has its own influence on the change of the whole system as components

The third chapter of the dissertation is devoted to "effective indicators of moral and moral education of the future teacher of vocational education". In this chapter, the effective levels of the process of spiritual and moral education of the future teacher of vocational education are shown.

One of the main factors that ensure the spiritual and moral education of the future teacher of vocational education is to raise the process of teaching subjects in the pedagogical direction to a high level. In the process of organizing practical work aimed at moral and moral education of future teachers of vocational education in higher educational institutions, experimental-test works were conducted on the basis of questions and answers, round tables and questionnaires among the respondents working in these educational institutions.

In the research work, opportunities of moral and moral education of students of the directions of Higher Education "use and repair of vehicles", "electrical energy", "light industry technology" were identified.

The main purpose of the experience-testing work organized to ensure moral and moral training of teachers of future professional education in higher educational institutions is to study the pre-and post – experience state of the level of moral and moral education of the students of these educational institutions and achieve full formation of moral and moral qualities in them.

In the process of carrying out the research, a total of 521 students from educational institutions, including Bukhara high technology engineering and Technical Institute, Karshi State University, Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, Bukhara State University were involved in the experimental work and their knowledge on moral and moral education was tested. Students were referred to experimental and control groups according to the principle of random selection. In the experimental groups, work was carried out on the basis of a questionnaire expressing the concepts of moral and moral education and the methodology for determining their knowledge. In the control groups, however, although

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general information was given about the issue under study at the beginning of the study, the experimental group provided a relatively in-depth and thorough knowledge.

In the process of acquisition of knowledge by teachers of future professional education in experimental and test works, in their spiritual and moral education, we based on the following criteria::

1. Knowledge of the meaning and essence of spirituality, enlightenment, morality, concepts.
2. Formation of a sense of respect for our national spiritual heritage.
3. To know our thinkers and their creativity.
4. Education in the spirit of traditions, loyalty to national and universal values.
5. Formation of feelings of humankind and fairness.
6. Love for the motherland, understanding of the social duty before Vatan.
7. Mutual respect, striving to increase spiritual-moral qualities.
8. Formulate the attitude to such qualities as kindness, generosity, mutual assistance.
9. To operate in the interest of society and to know its moral and moral requirements.

In the process of training in higher educational institutions, the formation of moral and moral qualities of future teachers of vocational education using the opportunities of technological approach is one of the most effective methods. The educational process, organized on the basis of a technological approach, must first serve to ensure the development of the spirituality of the personality of the teacher of the future professional education. Because in the technological approach in education-training, the ability of participants in the educational process to master, the variety of educational content, types of educational material, their cognitive activity, lack of uniformity of manifestations and other reasons are not hindered.

As a result of the study, the data of the control group were compared with the data of the experimental group. Comparative analysis was determined using techniques of self-assessment, rating, tests, observation, conversation, questionnaire, creation of problematic situations, as noted above. Comparative analysis showed that the results of the control group were significantly lower than those of the experimental-test groups in the results of educational work aimed at a specific goal. Especially at the end of the experiment, that is, the teachers of the future vocational education gave positive indicators at the time of graduating from a higher educational institution. 32% of the student gave a high result, while in the control group showed 18%. Hence, the system of educational

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influence shows that it turned out to be effective in practice: if at the beginning of the experiment there were 14% of students who gave a morally high level of performance, then at the end of the experiment it was 32%. The process of spiritual and moral development in the control group has not changed. Because the educational impact in these groups is not based on a specific goal, but on general requirements. Students in the control class lack such qualities as aspiration for the future, willpower, enthusiasm, courage, self-confidence.

In the experimental groups, the students set new life goals, brought up moral and moral qualities in themselves, as well as achieved a high level of moral and moral consciousness and behavior, acquired the skills of self-management.

Thus, the spiritual and moral upbringing of the teacher of the future professional education has effectively completed the experience-testing work. The level of moral and moral upbringing of the participants of the experimental groups was high, which confirmed the effectiveness of the methodology we conducted.

The results of the experimental and test work conducted with the aim of determining the moral and moral upbringing of the future teacher of vocational education are presented in the table below:

Table 1

Experience-test result indicators

Groups number of students level of knowledge acquisition

upper average lower

Experience 264 89 135 40

Control 257 67 82 108

For the mathematical – statistical analysis of these data, the method Student-Fisher was chosen.

For experimental and control groups, the modal values of the cursors are $MT=5$ and $MH=3$ respectively, that is, the difference between them is sufficient, since $MT > MH$. This, in turn, indicates in advance that even the appropriate medium values for these selections satisfy the conditions $X > Y$. We calculate them based on the following formulas:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^{n=3} n_i x_i = \frac{1}{264} (89 \cdot 5 + 135 \cdot 4 + 40 \cdot 3) = \frac{1}{264} (445 + 540 + 120) = \frac{1105}{264} = 4,1$$

$$\bar{Y} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^{n=3} n_i y_i = \frac{1}{257} (67 \cdot 5 + 82 \cdot 4 + 108 \cdot 3) = \frac{1}{257} (335 + 328 + 324) = \frac{987}{257} = 3,8$$

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So it turns out that the average mastering in the experimental group is greater than in the control group:

$$\bar{X} > \bar{Y}$$

Based on the above results, we calculate the quality indicators of experience-testing work.

$$\bar{X} = 4,1; \quad \bar{Y} = 3,8; \quad \Delta_{\text{м}} = 0,03; \quad \Delta_{\text{н}} = 0,05$$

More quality indicators:

$$K_{\text{эф}} = \frac{\bar{X} - \Delta_{\text{м}}}{\bar{Y} + \Delta_{\text{н}}} = \frac{4,1 - 0,03}{3,8 + 0,05} = \frac{4,07}{3,85} = 1,06 > 1;$$

$$K_{\text{эф}} = (\bar{X} - \Delta_{\text{м}}) - (\bar{Y} - \Delta_{\text{н}}) = (4,1 - 0,03) - (3,8 - 0,05) = 4,07 - 3,75 = 0,32 > 0;$$

From the results obtained, one can see that the criterion for assessing the effectiveness of training is suddenly the size and the criterion for assessing the level of cognition is the size from scratch.

From this it seems that the results of the experimental group are higher than those of the control group.

CONCLUSION

1. Theoretical sources devoted to the spiritual and moral training of teachers of future professional education, analysis of research work, practice of training teachers of future professional education, the results of a comprehensive study of their work activities showed that the development of a holistic system of spiritual and moral education of teachers of future professional education in higher educational institutions and theoretical justification of

2. The technological system of moral and moral education of teachers of future professional education was determined taking into account specific pedagogical and psychological characteristics. It was found out that these pedagogical and psychological characteristics allow the young professional education teacher to organize, design the educational process in a purposeful manner, to choose the educational tasks that serve the pupil rational, spiritual, physical and moral development.

3. The process of moral and moral education of teachers of future vocational education is a multifaceted system, it covers the content, Form, tools, methods and techniques of the system of training teachers of vocational education, teacher-reader relations, ways of organizing them in the order of subjects, teacher skills and personal qualities.

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4. In the process of spiritual and moral education of teachers of future professional education, the skills and professional skills of the teacher occupy a special place, for its formation it is desirable to organize the educational process on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies.

5. Effective forms and techniques of work carried out in moral and moral education of teachers of future professional education, in the auditorium and outside the auditorium were selected and methods of using educational tools were developed.

6. A system of lessons on the basis of interdisciplinary links was developed, aimed at spiritual and moral education with the help of additional information that allows to convey the subjects and their content to the minds of students included in the program of disciplines in the pedagogical direction. It was scientifically based on the fact that the opportunities of pedagogical disciplines in spiritual and moral education of teachers of future professional education are great.

7. It was determined that the process of education and training in moral and moral education of teachers of future professional education, didactic games that encourage teachers and students to communicate together, plays a special role.

8. The criteria for determining the level of moral and moral upbringing in future professional education teachers were developed in the course of the experimental and test work carried out on the research. The importance of moral and moral education in the preparation of teachers of future professional education was determined.

Based on the above conclusions, we recommend the following:

1. To achieve the improvement of the quality of training of teachers of vocational education by developing ways of increasing the effectiveness of teaching subjects in pedagogical direction in higher educational institutions.

2. Creation of information-visual materials in the subjects of pedagogical direction, enrichment of new versions of the texts of lectures on the basis of modern technologies.

3. To create a complex of scientific-methodical, popular literature, electronic manuals on improving moral and moral education of teachers of future professional education, carry out fundamental scientific research work on this problem.

4. Training of teachers of professional education, having acquired knowledge and professional skills by organizing the educational process in higher educational institutions in the direction of vocational education on the basis of advanced pedagogical technologies.

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Том 2, Выпуск 2, 29 Февраль

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